

COURSE INTEGRATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY

**Our experience as librarians partnering
with instructors to integrate virtual
reality in the Medical School curriculum**

Ryn Gagen, Brooke Olson, Merete Christianson, and Nicole Theis-Mahon

AGENDA

1 VIRTUAL REALITY (VR) IN MEDICAL EDUCATION AND LIBRARIES

2 OUR COURSE INTEGRATED PARTNERSHIP USING VR

3 CHALLENGES AND SUCCESSES!

VR IN MEDICAL EDUCATION

- anatomy instruction
- practicing communication skills
 - medical simulation
 - surgical training
- **building empathy**

VR IN OUR LIBRARY

The University of Minnesota Health Sciences Library moved to a new building in 2021, which includes a Virtual Reality Studio.

We also have a dedicated Academic Technologist and VR Program Lead (Charlie Heinz!)

VR FOR BUILDING EMPATHY: First-person immersive experiences of the patient perspective

Who You'll Embod

Beatriz Rogers has been a math teacher for nearly 4 decades. Beatriz enjoys spending time with her family (especially her grandson, Junior), cooking, and going to Mass every Sunday. Beatriz loves listening to music and is always ready to dance.

OUR COURSE PARTNERSHIP: Becoming a Doctor

COURSE PURPOSE:

Variety of sessions focusing on professional identity formation, reflective practice, and clinical skills.

COURSE FORMAT:

- 90-minute sessions
- no homework/prework
- elective students chose

INSTRUCTORS:

- Geriatric Education Specialist
- Clinical geriatrician co-facilitators
- Library staff!

AUDIENCE:

- 3rd and 4th-year medical students
- 20 students / session

SESSION DESIGN:

Students split into two groups, then switched activities halfway through:

Activity 1: In VR Studio taking turns in the VR experience while everyone watched on a large screen.

Activity 2: Interactive classroom activity about making sacrifices to simulate the feelings of loss associated with dementia.

CHALLENGES

VR Experience

This was most of our students' first experiences with VR. This was a great opportunity, but left relatively **little time to allow students time to acclimate and orient themselves to the technology and equipment.**

Software

All of our VR software is purchased and maintained through third-party vendors, leaving us **totally reliant on vendors** to fix bugs, update compatibility, set pricing and terms of our licenses, etc.

Hardware

At the time we introduced this class, the software (Embodied Labs) required the use of leap motion controllers for hand tracking, which **limited us to using the only compatible wired VR headset** we had (Valve Index)

Course Limitations

While working **with the existing course structure of the Medical School's curriculum, we have limited instruction time** with the students to allow every student to experience the full module content, so they took turns.

SUCCESSSES!

- Connection with a valuable instructor!
- Exposed most medical students to virtual reality for the first time!
- Students found the activities very emotionally salient and helpful (especially paired with discussions led by experienced gerontologists)
- Highlighted the variety of resources and tools available in the Libraries
- Created a lot of public interest in our VR resources, such as a major news story (which became a meme)

@minnesotamemes on Instagram

THE ROLE OF THE LIBRARIAN

Librarians collaborating with instructors for course integration of virtual reality

Ryn Gagen; Brooke Olson; Merete Christianson; Nicole Theis-Mahon

See end of article for authors' affiliations.

Background: Health science libraries have invested in virtual reality technology and spaces to support use of this technology for teaching, learning, and research. Virtual reality has many uses within health sciences education such as simulation, exploration and learning, and soft skills development. It can also be used to build empathy in health sciences students through applications that provide an immersive, first-person perspective.

Case Presentation: This case describes how a health sciences library and liaison librarians partnered with a course instructor to support a class utilizing the library's virtual reality resources. Librarians were collaborators in the development of the class and facilitated class sessions in the Virtual Reality Studio. Class sessions utilized the Beatriz Lab by Embodied Labs to increase empathy in medical students who were interested in working with geriatric or Alzheimer's patients.

Conclusion: Liaison librarians support teaching and learning through a variety of tools and resources, including virtual reality. By partnering with instructors, librarians can use their instruction and collection knowledge to design and facilitate classes that are meaningful and interactive. Virtual reality applications provide another resource that librarians can incorporate into their course-integrated instruction sessions.

Keywords: Libraries; Medical Education; Virtual Reality; Instruction; Librarians

BACKGROUND

Virtual reality (VR) is an immersive technology that provides unique opportunities for learning through the simulation of being physically present in computer-generated environments with realistic sensory experiences. The 2016 Horizon Report identified virtual reality as an emerging trend revolutionizing medical education, allowing students to visualize and interact with complex real-world data, train in adaptive immersive scenarios, and receive real-time feedback [1]. Today, VR is utilized in a variety of ways in medical education, such as augmenting anatomy instruction [2], teaching surgical training techniques [3], and enhancing empathy [4].

Virtual reality has potentially promising means for facilitating experiential learning, an area of emphasis for many academic libraries and in the health sciences [5]. Over the last two decades, libraries have increasingly transformed their role from repositories of information into centers for the creation of new knowledge [6]. As a

perceptions of patients by engaging users in sensory experiences that simulate the lived realities of medical conditions. For example, virtual reality's use as a perspective-taking educational tool has shown a demonstrated impact on empathy for people living with dementia [10].

VR simulations of patient experiences create unique opportunities for medical students to practice competencies and build empathy unavailable in other forms of training. For example, many medical school simulation programs include standardized patients, or actors, to play the part of a patient in medical scenarios while the students play the role of the health care provider. While this is important training, it does not put medical students in the shoes of the patient to help them understand the patient's lived experiences. The first-person perspective of wearing a VR headset can strongly influence students' affective response to patients with dementia through simulating disease symptoms, sensory distortions, internal narratives, and social frustration. This

THANK YOU!

Any questions?

← READ MORE!

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REFERENCES

Embodied Labs [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.embodiedlabs.com/>.

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